

THE CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT AND THE EXEMPLIFICATION OF THE IMPLEMENTATION IN THE ORGANIZATIONAL CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP

Author(s)*: Mircea Teodor POP¹, Miroslav SKUBAL², Delia Marcela POP³, Lidia FONAI⁴
Position: Prof., PhD¹, General Manager Eng², Assoc. Prof., PhD³, Eng⁴
University: University of Oradea^{1,3}, SC Niob Fluid s.r.o. Ostrožská, Czech Republic^{2,4}
Address: Oradea, Universitatii Str., No. 1, Romania, NIOB FLUID s.r.o., Ostrožská 1003, 687 25 Hluk, Česká Republika²
Email: popmt@uoradea.ro¹, skubal@niobfluid.cz², deliampop@gmail.com³, lidiafonai@yahoo.com⁴
Webpage: <http://www.uoradea.ro/>, <http://www.niobfluid.cz>

Abstract

Purpose - is to exemplify the way in which an industrial company responds to customer complaints, based on the application of the principles of customer relationship management.

Methodology/approach - applied research and development

Findings - implementing customer relationship management can generate organizational customer loyalty and involves researches, tests, redesign and implementations for new or improved products

Research limitations/implications - depending on the profile of industrial companies and of their customers, customizations of the implementation of customer relationship management are required.

Practical implications - the implementation at SC Niob Fluid s.r.o., Ostrožská, Czech Republic was analyzed, resulting in a case of good practice.

Originality/value - the approach to customer relationship management from the perspective of organizational customer orientation.

Key words: customer relationship management, loyalty, rotary spray head

Customer Relationship Management

The importance that customers have in the activity of companies is widely recognized, even in practice. This was highlighted in the management theory by Peter F. Drucker who spoke of the fact that the customer is at the heart of any company's strategy. Along with the economic, technical, technological, social evolution etc. specific to the last century, the customer-oriented management elements have also been conceptually developed, generating a new scientific field, that is the customer relationship management (CRM).

The customer relationship management is defined as a global process of creating and maintaining profitable customer relationships by ensuring a higher level of value and satisfaction for the customer, but which results in customer loyalty. At the same time, the levers of customer relationship management ensure the most efficient use of each contact/ customer, of each interaction between the company and the consumer to obtain direct mutual benefits from both parties. In its initial phase, the customer relationship management was defined as the activity of managing customer databases. Gradually, CRM evolved, and in addition to the activity of managing databases with customers, it extended its concerns to the management of detailed information about customers, in order to know their needs, preferences, desires etc. and, by fulfilling them, it is aimed at maximizing their fidelity and maintaining long-term profitable relationships.

Globalization, digitalization and current computerization have created the challenge for companies to manage numerous and very different customers, customers whom the company is interested to study and keep close by offering the right products and services and an adapted sales mode. But, globalization and digitalization have created great premises for development and companies that manage organizational customer relationships. For these customers, an optimal customer relationship

management implies a deeper, more detailed and more complex direct relationship with them. The following principles can be used to optimize these relationships:

- permanent provision (24 hours a day) of information related to products and services as well as about their use, with the provision of specialized technical assistance;
- identifying the way in which each client defines its quality and then creating service packages adapted to each client, oriented to their requirements and expectations;
- quick estimation and identification of potential problems (regardless of their nature) that may occur in the relationship with the client, this being recommendable even before they happen, as well as the way to treat them;
- creating a friendly mechanism for managing and resolving customer complaints as soon as possible.

In order to implement these principles and create a coherent and efficient CRM project, employees of the departments of Design, Production, Sales, Marketing, Financial-Accounting etc. are mobilized that is, all those who can generate value in the relationship with each customer.

The Description of the Organizational Context

Niob Fluid s.r.o. Company, based in Ostrožská, Hluk, Czech Republic (The Czech Republic also known by its short-form name, Czechia) is a manufacturer of stainless-steel fittings and valves (X5CrNi 18-10) for the food, pharmaceutical and chemical industry.

Niob Fluid s.r.o. was established in 1992 and since then the company has become a major manufacturer of hand, pneumatic or electric-operated three-way direct shut-off valves, of input fittings, ball valves, globe valves, check valves, filters, vacuum valves, limiting valves and other products made of stainless steel. The company also supplies manholes designed especially for tanks used in the food industry. Since 2014, it has also been a manufacturer of heating elements for the food industry.

The company's production is also oriented towards the manufacture of customized products. The company Niob Fluid s.r.o. produces customized accessories and equipment, which are not intended exclusively for the food industry.

The atypical products, which are most commonly ordered, include variants of valves with different connections, as well as special welded pipe assemblies.

The company is included in the category of small enterprises in the Czech Republic and currently has 52 employees. Niob Fluid s.r.o. is a limited liability company being managed by a general manager. A large part of Niob Fluid production, about 80% of exports are directed to Russia and Ukraine and about 20% of them are delivered to Poland, Romania and Italy.

The geographical location of the most important customers of Niob Fluid s.r.o. are presented in Figure 1.

One of the important customers of the company is company X whose object of activity is the filtration of beer, wine and other beverages. For that company, Niob Fluid s.r.o. produces the 360° spray head used for washing and disinfecting the tanks needed in the brewing process. All over the world, the legislation obliges food industry producers to strictly comply with rules and regulations that directly affect the health of consumers, as well as the quality of products. In this idea, strict procedures that aim at washing and disinfecting the necessary volumes in this industry are regulated. Before the appearance of these procedures for washing the tanks, specialized personnel disassembled the machine and then penetrated inside the tanks. The washing thus performed was of low efficiency, using numerous human and material resources and large amounts of washing solutions. In addition to these drawbacks, the risk of infestation caused by improper washing and the introduction of other pathogens into tanks has led to the elimination of this technology and its replacement by modern technologies based on computerization and automation.

Figure 1. Important customers of the company

The Description of the Cleaning - Disinfection Cycle of Liquid Food Products Tanks

The cleaning - disinfection cycle for the tanks in the food industry is performed with the help of a fluid jet spray head which is directed (360°) under pressure on their entire inner surface. The method is very efficient and allows compliance with quality, hygiene and food safety standards, while ensuring low cycle costs.

The spray head uses relatively small amounts of cleaning fluid, the working pressures being low (1-3 bar). The method can be used for washing tanks with a volume between 5 m³ and 50 m³ and due to the rotational movement of the fluid jet it is ensured a washing of the entire inner surface of the tank in a very short time.

The spray cycle begins by inserting the device through the tank inspection window and positioning it in the tank. The device must be connected to a centrifugal pump with adequate power and flow rate correlated with the dimensions of the tank. The washing system can be also connected to a reducer that impresses a rotational movement and thus distributes the washing solution on the tank ceiling, on the side walls and on its bottom. The presentation of an application that contains spray heads is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. 360° spray heads in the process of cleaning – disinfection

All the components of the spray head must be made of stainless steel. The nozzle in the cleaning head is a compact device that rotates axially, being driven in this movement by the cleaning agent due to the

arrangement of the slots through which the cleaning agent exits, as shown in Figure 2. The entire cleaning system - disinfection from a dairy using this method to sanitize milk cooling tanks / tanks is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Milk cooling tank/tank with automatic washing system

The meaning of the notations in figure 4 is the following: 1 - ventilation system; 2 - visiting cover; 3 - stirring system; 4 - agitator gear motor; 5 – 360° spray head; 6 - evaporator in construction; 7 - compression unit; 8 - control console for agitator temperature and speed; 9 and 10 - automatic washing system; 11 - tank body; 12 - adjustable legs.

In a first constructive variant, the 360° rotary spray head (Figure 2) was designed, manufactured and tested at Niob Fluid s.r.o. The components of the 360° spray head are made of stainless steel and are shown in Figure 4.

1. the lower part of the nozzle system;
2. the upper part of the nozzle system;
3. special bearing;
4. connecting piece through which the washing system is supplied and which is connected to a pump;
5. special bearing balls;
6. pin;
7. assurance element.

A longitudinal section through the special bearing (component 3 of Figure 5) is shown in Figure 5.

The body of the nozzle system consists of two components called the lower part (component 1 in Figure 4 and in Figure 6) and the upper part (position 2 in Figure 4 and in Figure 6) which are assembled by welding.

Figure 4. 360° Rotary spray head for pin assembly

3	Kulička 1.4404		Nerezová ocel (austenitická)	18	
2	5323-065-04	POUZDRO LOŽISKA	Nerezová ocel (austenitická)	1	
1	5323-065-03	VNITŘNÍ LOŽISKO	Nerezová ocel (austenitická)	1	
Poz	Název	Výkres-Norma-Popis	Materiál	Ks	Poznámka

Figure 5. Longitudinal section through the special bearing

2	5323-poletovar-065-02	HORNÍ POKROKLE	Nerezová ocel (austenitická)	1	
1	5323/065/02	SPODNÍ SPRCHA	Nerezová ocel (austenitická)	1	
Poz	Název	Výkres-Norma-Popis	Materiál	Ks	Poznámka

Figure 6. Body of the nozzle system without machined slots

The slots, with a different inclination and positioning, are obtained by milling at dimensions that are in accordance with those in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Dimensions and position of the slots for the nozzle system body

Implementing the Principles of Customer Relationship Management

Niob Fluid s.r.o. is attentive to customer relationship management and actively implements the principles defined by customer relationship management. In this sense, for its products, the company provides technical assistance permanently specialized to its customers, tries to adapt its products according to their requirements, estimates problems of any kind that may arise in relation to them, manages and quickly resolves any complaints.

Also, Niob Fluid s.r.o. cultivates a relationship based on trust with its customers that results from the open interaction with them, an effective partnership in making the products they need, an effective communication etc.

With all the simulations and tests performed by Niob Fluid on the entire manufacturing flow of the products, even in the design stage, some problems may sometimes arise in their operation, aspects that are noticed by customers. These problems can be noticed by watching, for a longer time, the way in which the products behave in operation. This situation also occurred in the case of the partnership with company X.

Presentation of a Technical Problem Identified by the Customer

For this first constructive variant of the 360° spray head, notifications and complaints were received from the customer Niob, company X, the first to use the 360° spray head for washing and disinfecting the tanks/tanks used in their own production processes. The problem was stopping the spray head from

rotating during the washing cycle, which had as consequences: the remaining of uncleaned residues in tanks, the existence of non-hygienic surfaces and the possibility of microbial infestation of newly stored or processed products. It was also claimed that the washing radius of 1.5 - 2 meters, described in the technical documentation of the spray head, is not reached during the washing process, which led to poor cleaning on the side surfaces of the tanks. These problems arose although the customers complied with the requirements of the technical data sheet of operation of the spray head where it was specified to ensure a working pressure of 1 to 3 bar, in which case the manufacturer guarantees to obtain a washing radius of 1.5 to 2 meters.

Thus, based on the received notifications, the company Niob Fluid started a process of analysing the causes of these phenomena and numerous tests were made (images from the 360° spray head tests are shown in Figure 8). The result of the carried out tests led to a first conclusion, namely that at an inclination of less than 2° (degrees) of the spray head during the washing process this is locked and in this way the nozzle system does not rotate. The locking takes place because the ball sleigh (of the special bearing) touches the outer wall and thus a sliding friction occurs between them which causes the balls of the special bearing to no longer fulfil their functional role.

Figure 8 - Images from the 360° spray head test

Also, another conclusion resulting from the tests performed, which could determine or contribute to blocking the rotation of the nozzle system body, was related to the section of the channel through which the washing device is fed.

In fluid dynamics, Bernoulli's Law states that an increase in the velocity of a liquid occurs simultaneously with a decrease in pressure or a decrease in the potential energy of the fluid.

Following the findings of the tests, it was concluded that a 360° spray head redesign is needed to eliminate the reported drawbacks.

The Results Obtained by Redesign and Feedback from the Company's Client

The first redesigned component was the special bearing which in the new version was designed as having two rows of balls, which will determine a better stability of the spray head during the process and, thus, the influence of its angles of tilt during operation will be reduced. The resulting variant is shown in figure 9.

4	5324P-6,35	Kulička 6,35mm	Nerezová ocel (austenitická)	36	
3	5323P-065-05	HORNÍ KRYT LOŽISKA	Nerezová ocel (austenitická)	1	
2	5323P-065-04	SPODNÍ KRYT LOŽISKA	Nerezová ocel (austenitická)	1	
1	5323P-065-03	TĚLESO LOŽISEK	Nerezová ocel (austenitická)	1	
Poz	Název	Výkres-Norma-Popis	Materiál	Ks	Poznámka

Figure 9. Special redesigned bearing with two rows of balls

Another change made was that by which a variation of the section of the washing liquid circulation channel was made, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Change of section through the body of the spray head to the redesigned version of the 360° spray head

The redesign of the special bearing, which in this constructive variant has two rows of balls, so a larger axial gauge, also determined the need to redesign the connecting parts in order to maintain the total height of the spray head. The redesign was made for all types of assembly of 360° spray head components: pin assembly, welding assembly and thread assembly. These are shown in Figures 11 (Pin Assembly), 12 (Weld Assembly) and 13 (Thread Assembly).

Figure 11. Pin assembly

Figure 12. Weld assembly

Figure 13. Thread assembly

The final results of redesigning the special bearing (the new constructive solutions, corresponding to the three types of assembly) are presented in figures 14 - 16.

Figure 14. Head assembled with pins

Figure 15. Head assembled by welding

Figure 16. Head assembled with thread

After redesigning, there were performed tests by which the redesigned 360° spray heads were tested in several operating positions, for this purpose a special tank being used, as shown in figure 17. These tests have shown that the improvements have solved all the problems noticed, the redesigned 360° spray heads working properly in any position in which they are inserted into the tank.

Figure 17. Tank for final testing of redesigned 360° spray heads

Conclusions

For companies that make products or provide services for organizational customers, customer relationship management becomes a mandatory element to ensure market success. This is accentuated by the fact that the development of a company is no longer necessarily given by the acquisition of new customers but by obtaining the loyalty of the existing ones. Implementing the principles of customer relations is a long-term process that starts from simple customer complaints to the inclusion in the organizational culture of respect for customers and treating them as collaborators to obtain the most appropriate products for their work.

Also, the customer relationship management must be approached as part of the company's business strategy because it is relevant and profitable for the company only insofar as it contributes to achieving the company's objectives and generating value both for it and the customer. This overlaps with the attitude of collaboration and partnership existing between the manufacturer and the customer with maximizing long-term customer satisfaction and loyalty.

For Niob Fluid s.r.o., the implementation of the principles of customer relationship management is already performing and has led to its success and development on the market.

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